

Historical Performance Practice in Electroacoustic Music through Restoring Lost Media — “Interface Concerto” by Shigenobu Nakamura as a Case Study

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Abstract

This paper discusses a case study of Japanese electroacoustic music that has become technologically obsolete and consequently unperformable in the present day. While Japan produced numerous electronic and electroacoustic works throughout the late twentieth century, the majority of these compositions face significant challenges in being realized with contemporary technologies. This difficulty arises largely because the majority of works were not systematically archived or professionally managed, resulting in the obsolescence and disappearance of the specialized hardware and software on which they depended.

In response to this situation, the author has undertaken a project dedicated to the restoration of such unperformable compositions. As a case study of this project, this paper focuses on the restoration of Shigenobu Nakamura’s (中村滋延, 1950–) “Interface Concerto” for Keyboard and MIDI System (1992). This work originally employed custom-developed MIDI devices, specialized sound modules, and composition software. Since none of these tools remains operational as of 2025, “Interface Concerto” effectively became a lost work. The present study aims to re-establish its performability by analyzing the composition, with particular attention to its use of now-outdated MIDI technology, and by detailing the restoration process through which it has been revived.

Additionally, through the contemporary restoration attempt of “Interface Concerto”, this paper will explore the definition of “restoration”, departing from debates surrounding historically informed performance practices. In response to the EMS 2025 theme of “Electroacoustic Music as Interdisciplinary Practices”, it begins from the field of historically informed performance in early music – often regarded as antithetical to electroacoustic music – and anticipates pathways toward future interdisciplinary discussions across diverse domains.

1. Introduction

Since the standardization of MIDI in 1983, numerous composers have explored its possibilities, resulting in a wide range of works. Compositions for MIDI keyboards or MIDI Disklaviers represent representative examples of this development.

Japanese composers have similarly embraced MIDI technology. For instance, Masahiro Miwa (三輪眞弘, b. 1958) composed “Gesänge des Ostens (東の唄)” (1992) for two

Disklaviers, one pianist and a computer, in which the Disklaviers transmit MIDI signals to the computer. Likewise, Suguru Goto (後藤英, b. 1966) employed MIDI signals to control panning across four surround speakers in “Transformation II” (1992).

Several composers developed bespoke MIDI devices tailored to their works. Kazuo Uehara (上原和夫, 1949-2022), for example, created sound and light objects controlled via MIDI keyboard in “Chaos Alpha” (1992). Shigenobu Nakamura (中村滋延, b. 1950), in collaboration with Yoichi Nagashima (長嶋洋一, b. 1958), devised the MIDI device called “Hyper N-5” for multiple compositions; this system converted MIDI signals into automated note sequences. Regrettably, most such devices are now unavailable, having been lost or damaged.

This paper examines the lost “Hyper N-5” and Nakamura’s “Interface Concerto”, which featured it. Despite the device’s absence, the author has restored it using the visual programming language plugdata, based on surviving documentation and testimonials. The subsequent chapter details the restoration process and its underlying aesthetics.

2. Interface Concerto and Hyper N-5

This chapter presents a comprehensive overview of “Interface Concerto” and the Hyper N-5, with particular emphasis on their technical dimensions.

Composed in 1992, “Interface Concerto” features a MIDI keyboard, multiple MIDI sound modules, and a Macintosh computer. As befits its title as a “Concerto”, it sets the MIDI keyboard performer against electronic sounds emanating from loudspeakers. The work comprises nine sections and lasts approximately eight and a half minutes. It integrates two primary sonic elements: pre-composed fixed electronic sounds utilizing General MIDI timbres, and live electronic sounds generated in real time – triggered by the MIDI keyboard and automatically realized via the Hyper N-5. The pre-composed layer persists throughout, interwoven with the live elements. An Emu Proteus/2 MIDI sound module, interfaced with the computer, rendered the pre-composed material.

The composition further employs the bespoke MIDI device Hyper N-5, developed in collaboration with Yoichi Nagashima, an engineer from KAWAI. Upon receiving triggered notes from the MIDI keyboard (as notated in the score), the Hyper N-5 autonomously determined pitch, duration, and velocity parameters. It then transformed each input into a pre-programmed sequence of one to eight notes – defined within Cycling ‘74’s software “M” – and routed the output through loudspeakers. This mechanism elevated the performer’s straightforward execution into a virtuosic, multifarious performance. The Hyper N-5 interfaced with an “M” patch for operation, with sound result handled by two KAWAI K4r MIDI modules. These sources – pre-composed sounds from the Emu Proteus/2 and live electronics sounds from the KAWAI K4r – converged via an audio mixer, emerging through loudspeakers amplified by reverberation effects.

Figure 1 Original technical rider for “Interface Concerto”, as included in the score.
 Reproduced with kind permission from the composer.

Regrettably, these MIDI devices – the Hyper N-5, Emu Proteus/2, and KAWAI K4r – are no longer available. Both the Emu proteus/2 and KAWAI K4r are now obsolete, while no blueprints or photographs of the Hyper N-5 survive. Detailed documentation proved elusive, as both Nakamura and Nagashima have destroyed most of their archival materials. Fortunately, a CD recording of the original performance exists, with the composer having uploaded it to YouTube¹. This provides online access to the original sound, allowing informed analysis of the system’s functionality and timbral results.

The author initiated the restoration project of “Interface Concerto” based on this surviving CD recording and the original score. The subsequent chapter describes the detailed restoration procedure.

¹ NAKAMURA, Shigenobu (中村滋延), Shigenobu Nakamura: Interface Concerto for MIDI keyboard and computed MIDI Synthesizer(1992), YouTube, <https://youtu.be/-YmijuY77sE?si=4tCjxsgnypILkr4x>.

3. Restoring Interface Concerto

According to Nakamura, the Hyper N-5 employed in “Interface Concerto” features a function that “can emit the note eight times repeatedly which is specified by the MIDI keyboard. In other words, Hyper N-5 can produce eight echoes from a single note²”. This information enables a detailed analysis of the score’s elements, which comprises three staves from top to bottom: the Hyper N-5 part (automatically triggered), the live MIDI keyboard part, and the pre-composed electronic sounds part.

Comparison of the recording and score reveals that the Hyper N-5 transforms MIDI keyboard-triggered notes into sequences of one to eight notes, as notated in the upper staff relative to middle C (C4) – totaling 56 such series. Auditory analysis confirms that triggering a specific note on the MIDI keyboard transposes the corresponding series accordingly, with output via the KAWAI K4r. For instance, on page 14, measure 81 (see Figure 2), the upper staff shows repeating C4 and F4 as the baseline. Playing C5 in the middle staff transposes the series up an octave (resulting in repeating C5 and F5); subsequently playing F5 transposes it a perfect fourth higher from C5 (resulting in repeating F5 and Bb5), with the sequence continuing thereafter.

Figure 2 Score excerpt from page 14, measure 81 (top) and author’s notated realization (bottom). “Hyp.” refers to Hyper N-5, “Keyb.” refers to the MIDI keyboard. Score reproduced with kind permission from the composer.

² NAKAMURA, Shigenobu (中村滋延), Interface Concerto, Private edition, 1992, Instruction Page.

Based on this analysis, the author restored the Hyper N-5 functionality using plugdata, a visual programming language. To replicate the device’s MIDI keyboard input detection and automated performance system, the [else/score2] object (hereafter “[score2]”) – a text-score-based sequencer – was employed. The [score2] object reads scores as text files storing parameters such as measure, tempo, time signature, note duration, and related attributes, then sequences their playback accordingly.

For instance, as shown in Figure 3, the text score corresponds to the 11th series in measure 11 of the original score. The first line specifies the measure; the second, the tempo (BPM = 60); the third, the persistent time signature (1/4); and subsequent lines, individual note data as numerical values. From the third line onward, these values sequentially represent note duration, pitch, dynamics, and program number from left to right. Persistent program numbers (or program and dynamic values) may be omitted in subsequent lines. The successively appearing note values from top to bottom in the pitch column raise the actual pitch by semitones; meanwhile, the numbers appearing in the dynamics column inversely attenuate the velocity.

Thus, the text score in Figure 3 may be interpreted as follows: at BPM = 60 and 1/4 time, note values decelerate from eighth notes (1/8) to half notes (1/2) – affecting a ritardando – while pitch ascends +14 semitones and dynamics diminish by -35 (decrescendo).

Figure 3 Score excerpt (Hyper N-5 part), page 2, measure 11 from “Interface Concerto” (left) and transcribed text score derived from the original score (right).
Score reproduced with kind permission from the composer.

Figure 4 restored patch for the Hyper N-5.

The Author generated 56 text scores corresponding to the 56 series in this manner, then programmed a plugdata patch to sequentially load and perform them via the [score2] object. This patch comprises four principal components. The first (①) specifies the text file to load and distributes its parameters across the relevant objects. The second (②) detects MIDI keyboard input, displaying the performed note and velocity values (a) alongside the offsets to be added or subtracted in the following sequence (b). The third (③) computes the resultant values (a+b) or (a-b) for immediate playback. These are routed to the [noteout] object, resulting in sound via plugdata’s internal MIDI instruments – which substitute for the original KAWAI K4r modules. The fourth (④) modulates the program number to vary timbral characteristics.

The restored Hyper N-5 patch integrates into the main “Interface Concerto” patch (see Figure 5), orchestrating all elements. The graphical user interface features two keyboards: “IN” displays live MIDI keyboard input in real time, while “OUT” shows notes generated by the restored Hyper N-5. Performers may load specific cues and initiate playback from desired

points via the white “CUE” slider for rehearsal purposes. Volume control resides in the black “VOL” slider. All cues proceed automatically from the initial cue to the final over time upon a single press of the yellow “GO” toggle button, with each parameter transitioning accordingly. Current cue and series information appear at the patch’s upper left. All systems and parameters are initialized upon pressing the “GO” toggle button again to untoggle it.

Figure 5 Main patch (front window) of the restored “Interface Concerto”.

The fixed electronic sound layer – another core compositional element – has likewise been restored using contemporary General MIDI timbres. The author transcribed the score and generated a MIDI file via MuseScore Studio 4, a music notation program. This MIDI file was subsequently imported into Cakewalk by BandLab, a digital audio workstation, where the notes were rendered with virtual instruments including “Cakewalk TTS-1 (Roland)”, “The Gong (SampleScience)”, and “BBC Symphony Orchestra (Spitfire)”. The resulting audio was exported as a WAV file and integrated into the patch, activating upon the first cue (that is, loading of the initial text score).

Figure 6 Restoration of “Interface Concerto” fixed electronics sound file via MIDI mockup in Cakewalk by BandLab, using a MIDI file from MuseScore Studio 4.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

The temporal distance of approximately seventy years, spanning from the dawn of Japanese electronic music in the 1950s to the 2020s, may seem comparatively small when compared with the large gap between the 17th century Baroque era and the present day in European art music. Yet, in the field of electronic music, those seventy years have produced a technological and cultural rupture as profound as that between these two epochs of orchestral tradition. In other words, just as keyboard works originally composed for instruments such as the clavichord or harpsichord are now performed on the modern Piano, similar practices have emerged within electronic music.

Given that many of the media and devices used in early electronic music have been lost or are no longer reproducible, it has become common practice to explore new forms of re-performance using currently available technologies. For instance, Yasushi Akutagawa’s (芥川也寸志, 1925-1989) “GX Concerto”, originally composed for the Yamaha GX-1 Electone, was re-performed in 2022 by the Orchestra Triptyque using the Yamaha ELS-02X. Similarly, in Toshiro Mayuzumi’s (黛敏郎, 1929-1997) “Campanology for Multified Piano”, Hideaki Isobe (磯部英彬, b. 1982) programmed Max patches to emulate various hardware configurations, enabling pianist Ichiro Nodaïra (野平一郎, b. 1953) to realize the work’s first staged performance. Both examples constitute significant precedents in that they pursue restoration and re-performance of past works not through physical reconstruction of the original hardware, but through engagement with contemporary technological environments following the composer’s death. These cases not only demonstrate how historical electronic music can be reinterpreted and performed through the technologies of the present but also raise critical questions about the nature of authenticity in such processes – namely, what

defines the “original” work, and how much transformation should be considered acceptable in its restoration and re-performance.

The present restoration of “Interface Concerto” likewise confronts unresolved questions concerning the authenticity of the work. In this restoration, hardware such as the Hyper N-5 and MIDI sound modules has been emulated primarily through software based on plugdata, resulting in a material discrepancy between the original work and the version proposed in this study. Moreover, the degree of sonic fidelity relies heavily on the author’s own subjective judgement, which imposes clear limits on any objective assessment of the acoustic similarity between the original and the restored version. For this reason, further discussion is therefore needed to determine if this work can truly be called a “restoration” in the strict sense.

In addressing the question of this work’s authenticity, the author draws inspiration from longstanding debates surrounding historically informed performance practices. The contemporary practice of performing Johann Sebastian Bach or Domenico Scarlatti’s harpsichord works on modern pianos similarly arises from the physical unavailability of original instruments, coupled with the Piano’s ability to inherit harpsichord characteristics while enabling far greater sonic diversity. Although most of historically informed performances using historical harpsichords persist, the widespread acceptance of Baroque music on modern pianos – despite timbral and functional disparities – suggests that contemporary priorities favor expressive rendering of the work’s core elements (such as pitch, duration, rhythm) over precise replication of its historical auditory profile.

For “Interface Concerto”, restoration to its “original state” became impossible after the Hyper N-5 was discarded. Nevertheless, recreating the hardware from surviving documentation remained a feasible option. Yet the author’s decision to pursue software emulation via plugdata stemmed from positioning it as a contemporary medium similar to the Piano’s role in harpsichord repertoire – thereby exploring its potential as a feasible substitute. In other words, this restoration represents a practice of updating the historical instrument (Hyper N-5) through modern computing and the plugdata programming environment, thereby inheriting its era-specific qualities while advancing them forward.

Here, the author proposes a new definition of restoration practices. Three distinct criteria for restoration can be established: “physical restoration”, which physically recreates the equipment and structures of the era; “sonic restoration”, which replicates the acoustic output; and “practical retrostaion”, which rebuilds compositional approaches, conceptual frameworks, and operational systems, adapting them to contemporary contexts. This “practical restoration” therefore, may also be termed “adapted restoration” given its adaptive nature to the present era. The focus of this paper lies with “practical restoration”, which does not necessarily aim for complete replication of the original’s physical form or sonic characteristics.

In the practical restoration of “Interface Concerto”, following debates in historically informed performance practice, emphasis was placed not on mere imitation of past music or instruments, but on translating the work’s spirit and intent into contemporary terms. If, as Nikolaus Harnoncourt insisted, “Music is linked to a particular time; it is the living expression of its own period and can be completely understood only by its contemporaries³”, then preserving and reperforming historical legacies demands new musical translations adapted to

³ HARNONCOURT Nikolaus, *Baroque music today : music as speech : ways to a new understanding of music*, Oregon, Amadeus Press, 1988, p. 16.

the contemporaneity of the performance moment. As the acoustic and technical elements of past works are refreshed within modern media environments, provided that core elements such as pitch and rhythm, along with their historical and ideological contexts, are sufficiently inherited, such restoration can be evaluated as retaining a form of authenticity as practical restoration. This positions it as a feasible method for restoration in the present day.

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